

WORKING WITH ACCOUNTING AND AUDITING TEXTS BASED ON ACADEMIC READING SKILLS

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Abstract: Like all academic texts, those in accounting and auditing come with their own complexities, structures, and terminologies. Therefore, professionals should have some reading skills in order to master related documents. This thesis delves into some of the methods used to ease the process of understanding professional papers and documents of accounting and auditing.

Keywords: importance of academic reading, literacy, useful skills for accountants and auditors, text analyzing, academic reading, evaluating ability.

Introduction

Imagine an accountant misinterpreting a single line in a financial regulation—one mistake could cost a company millions. That is why academic reading skills are not optional — they're essential.

Accounting and auditing documents first emerged during the period between 1300 and 1850, which is referred to as Double-Entry Bookkeeping Era (1300-1850) in the history of accounting. At first, the accounting texts contained initial chart of accounts and some other simpler calculations. But then from the Theory-Practice Era (1850-1900) accounting started holding legal status and terms, like *differentiation of the chart of accounts, balance, profit, cost price, production costs*, were gradually

introduced into the field of accounting. This, in turn, created a need for having academic reading and comprehension skills for accountants and auditors.

Moreover, accountants do several important tasks including understanding complex concepts, analyzing, evaluating the validity of financial information and audit reports and making effective decisions based on them. On the other hand, accountants always need to be aware of changes in laws, standards and best practices because the field is constantly evolving due to them. In order to reach all the standards, professionals should read academic articles, research papers and government regulations which highly require academic reading skills.

This thesis aims to explore the role of academic reading skills in accounting and auditing, review research supporting their importance, and present practical methods to improve those skills.

Literature review

Reading Ability and Success in Accounting Program (H. Choy and D. Derrick, 2018), this article summarizes the result of an experiment examining the correlation between reading to learn ability and academic performance of accounting students and says the effect was positive, subject-specific reading ability was with respect to GPA. It found subject-specific reading ability as impactful for the academic performance of students rather than general reading ability which showed no impact.

According to E. Evans and B. Rigby, Macquarie University of Australia has practiced a study system for improving the literacy of students with second-year students of accounting and auditing. The reason was unexpected low results of newly added accounting and auditing subjects. The authorities of the university had waited for improvement in several accounting skills of students, but this wasn't present mainly because they were ill-equipped to read and understand many of the articles and case studies prescribed for the course.

They used overall 6 articles during the whole course that were written by professors of the university. Articles were to be read by the students, and there were some questions and tasks for them to answer. They were aimed at improving the

students' literacy skills (academic reading and writing) step by step with questions being slightly more difficult in each article. In the end, when answers to questions from Articles #1 and #6 were compared, it was clear that students had understood the importance of analyzing questions by using topic, focusing and instruction words. They were answering the questions in a structured way, and this was not evident in relation to Article #1.

In the Article named "Reading and Understanding Academic Research in Accounting: A Guide for Students" by G. Teresa and P. Jason, the core aim mainly focuses on bridging the gap between practitioners and academics in the field of accounting. It suggested several steps for effectively reading academic articles for practitioners who think it is a waste of time. It also proves why academic research is important, even for practitioners, saying 'Academic research looks at how accounting affects the world around us and how the world affects accounting. As a result, it can provide powerful information and insights for regulators, auditors, tax consultants, and other practicing accountants'¹.

At first, it says, we should read the abstract, introduction and conclusion before the main parts of an article. This helps us determine the question being asked in it and why that question is important. Then, making note of the important aspects of the paper for reference while reading the rest of the paper.

Methodology

According to Helen Choy and Deirdre J. Derrick, we can conclude that the importance of academic reading has been proven many times. While the first two articles present their research on accounting students who were taught academic reading skills and achieved certain results in their performances, the third one analyzes why real experienced accountants should also read articles and research papers related to their field.

¹ Gordon, Teresa P. and Porter, Jason C. (2009) "Reading and Understanding Academic Research in Accounting: A Guide For Students,"Global Perspectives on Accounting Education: Vol. 6: Iss. 1, Article 1. Available at: <http://digitalcommons.bryant.edu/gpae/vol6/iss1/1>

In these conducted experiments, the organizers helped students with specially prepared reading materials and experienced tutors. What differentiates their way of solving the problem is that they worked together, with a group of professionals, and created a huge system of students and tutors. Now, in this part of the thesis, we are going to review some basic methods and techniques that can be carried out individually by everyone.

The Pomodoro Technique for Focus

Academic reading should begin with a clear purpose and a focused preparation to apply the most appropriate strategies. In order to get the full of what we need from a text that we are reading, we must direct our full attention to it. This, of course, can be attributed to accounting papers and documents as well. One of the ways to achieve sustained concentration is Pomodoro technique which is recognized to be effective all over the world, and a lot of people have been benefiting from it in their academic and professional purposes. It is developed by Francesco Cirillo in the late 1980s. It is named after the tomato-shaped kitchen timer Cirillo used as a university student (pomodoro is Italian for tomato), this technique aims to improve productivity and focus by breaking work into manageable intervals.

The core idea of Pomodoro technique is to set a timer when doing a task and resting, and to direct one's full attention to the task. For doing a specific task, it is recommended to set a timer for 25 minutes and 5 minutes for rest/break. It also suggests that after repeating the process three times, it is good to extend the break to 30 minutes and take a mental break. Here, the word break is not referring to anything related to scrolling social media, which again challenges the brain, but to something that literally lets the brain rest, such as enjoying the view of nature, talking to someone about social life and even just lying and resting with a clear mind. If this aspect is overlooked, the technique becomes ineffective because the brain needs a real rest after some time of active work.

Effective Active Reading Strategies

Even if one has a good focus, they cannot read much if they are not interested or skilled enough to understand. Therefore, along with focus, we should consider several basic strategies, such as making predictions, visualizing content, asking questions, and summarizing, that make the process of reading interesting and engaging. In order to keep active while reading, it is important to underline or highlight key points as well as keep them reasonable. After reading a paragraph or section, try to summarize it briefly in your own words and paraphrase complex ideas to test understanding.

As well as the generally accepted methods, we can apply SQ3R method which gives a step-by-step guide to the readers (diagram 1).

Diagram 1

Discussion

Surveying over the full text - looking at titles, headings, tables, diagrams – gives us the opportunity to obtain an overview of the full text, and this step usually takes merely 3-5 minutes. Then, asking questions about what is going to be discussed in the text enables us to have a specific purpose in reading, which is answering the given questions. The third step is reading actively and seeking the answers, which is the main part of the whole process. In order to get the full meaning of what is read, turning the input into output is a good way. It means trying to explain what we understood to anyone or even no one, just ourselves; this is the 4th stage of the

strategy. One of the important parts is to review the content again after some time, to avoid the risk of losing a treasure.

This strategy is more appropriate for academic papers, which are designed to learn something new and require a clear focus and understanding, than documents that are mainly created for informing.

These given techniques do not show their impact if one does not read regularly; consistency is always the key. Quantity does not have to be many when one is a starter, try to read academic texts daily, even for 15 minutes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this thesis has demonstrated the critical importance of academic reading skills in accounting and auditing. As the field keeps changing and becoming more complex, it's really necessary for professionals to understand various texts like standards, research papers, and legal documents. The literature clearly proves that both students and practicing accountants benefit a lot from reading academic materials. Also, the techniques I shared—like the Pomodoro method for better focus and the SQ3R strategy for active reading—can really help make the reading process easier and more effective.

What matters most is being consistent. Even reading for just 15 minutes a day can make a big difference. These skills are not only beneficial for scholars, they're also really useful for staying updated and making smart decisions in the real accounting world. That's why academic reading isn't just something extra—it's something every future accountant needs.

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